

Life Skills VR: Life Skills for Employment in COVID-19 Era through VR Innovation

Data Management Plan

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Project abstract: The disruptive effects of the COVID-19 outbreak have impacted almost all sectors of our society. Tertiary education is no exception. In a study by Aucejo et al (2020) about 1500 students reported that the outbreak had large negative effects on students' current labour market participation and expectations about post-college labour outcomes. All issues related to pandemics have increased stress and anxiety leading to mental health among the young generation which has less experience of coping with stress. That is why is important to help them realise their strengths, develop missing skills and boost their confidence which will ultimately help in avoiding mental health-related issues by combining the VR technology and John Holland's personality criteria known as RIASEC – according to which people and work environments can be classified according to six basic types: Doers (Realistic), Thinkers (Investigative), Creators (Artistic), Helpers (Social), Persuaders (Enterprising) or Organizers (Conventional). RIASEC provides young people an opportunity to understand what areas they are inclined to succeed. The application of the RIASEC is combined with the development of key skills (Ziarati, 2020) which gives job applicants a greater chance of finding and keeping a job such as i) developing and managing self, ii) working as a member of a team, iii) communicating effectively, iv) maintaining physical and mental fitness, v) applying technology, vi) managing time, vii) defining and solving problems and viii) design skills. Thus, the proposed project intends to take full advantage of VR both as a tool to identify interest and strength, to develop key life skills required by the labour market and understand in which occupation they can excel and have a bright future. With a set of well-thought tests, the proposed app will allow users to take part in carefully organised quizzes that they will experience for themselves without getting bored or finding it dreadfully dull. Moreover, this project will allow users to know the missing skills and able them to focus on the important aspects by themselves and therefore able them to eliminate skills mismatching and develop key skills. Also, by knowing their strong points Generation C will be able to develop themselves to higher levels in seeking and retaining good and well-paid jobs.

Keywords: Employment; Skills development; Virtual reality innovation

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1. Output summary (Data collection)

The proposed project intends to take full advantage of Virtual Reality to help Gen-C be able to learn their inclination towards jobs and hunt for occupations while playing a game. This project is financed by Erasmus+ Programme and responds to all existing requirements related to the RDM and Protection of Personal Data. The project development will be under the Ethics Committee Regulations, which will be defined and described in the next version of the DMP. All members of the project follow the established, updated and monitored Data Management Plan during the development of the work and after its finalization.

The data collected/produced will be important in both scientific and social dimensions. This project, by combining the rising VR technology and Holland's RIASEC code, takes evaluating the youth's potential to a new level. Ultimately our aim is to tackle the youth unemployment rates in the UN countries by snipping the problem at the core in an innovative and refreshing way to create happy, satisfied and knowledgeable employees in their qualifications and thus creating happy and satisfied employers. The data of this project can be reused in other research studies, not only in Educational and Computer Science domains but in other social sciences domains such as Sociology, Political and Economic Science. Furthermore, will be useful for administration/policy makers (national, European and international), student organisations (national, European and international), employment agencies, careers guidance centres, chamber of commerce, industrial associations, VET providers, NGO and training institutions also can reuse the project results for implementation of the VR-system in their workflows.

Creating a virtual atmosphere and making the target audience test the RIASEC code can give them the opportunity to use the experience and knowledge gained in the real world and it can create a variety of RIASEC code situations. Youth perceptions can be changed easily thanks to virtual reality and they may be triggered to use the combative natural instincts by creating an atmosphere like in this application. With this VR experience, their sense of wonder can be addressed and the desire for discovery within each individual can also be triggered. Based on the knowledge that people have natural instincts to solve mysteries and puzzles and they attract the attention of people all over the world, this project is designed as a tool aimed to increase the interest in finding the right job of the younger generation, with an interdisciplinary approach, this project involves academicians from various disciplines to work together for the same purpose. With well-thought games and quizzes, the proposed app will let the users understand themselves better and choose a path according to their strengths and interest.

The project contains different steps of its development and they can be divided into 5 principal phases:

1. Preparation and analysis of the needs;
2. Development of the VR system
3. Curriculum;
4. Testing phase; Analysis of the results and improvements;
5. Dissemination of the results.

Each phase collects and produces different types of data, with different types of methodology and tools used, and will require different types of data management.

Phase 1. During this phase, the partners will identify key target groups in their countries. The target groups will be contacted by partners to participate in the survey and follow up interviews in focus groups. The aim of these activities will be to collect their needs and requirements to generate requirements and specifications for VR App. All activities that included users will be started after the explanation of the project goals, and the purpose of the data collection. Moreover, users need to assign informed consent.

The methodologies for the need analysis should be:

- A research questionnaire from all partner countries (min. 25/partner)
 - Life Skills VR – Questionnaire for Employers/Career Advisors/HR/Teachers/ Recruitment Agencies using the platform of LimeSurvey Software
 - Life Skills VR - Youth Survey
- Focus groups in partner countries (min. 2/partners)
- Interviews with NGO and public bodies in all partner countries.

The need analysis report will include:

- A realistic view of the current status of the youth to recognise their talents and abilities so that they find a future occupation in which they can use their qualifications to the fullest and be satisfied and happy in what they do.
- An analysis of the youth's behaviour model whilst searching for their future occupation.
- Guidelines and suggestions from the target group about how other outputs will be developed.

RAW data: surveys answers, interviews results (video recording with interviewers is not defined yet, it will be described in more detail in the next version of DMP)

Transcription video: in case the video recording, they will be transcripts and processed

Processed data: RAW data after their processing (e.g. anonymization, codification, elimination of all sensitive, personal data that can identify a person); processed transcripts without any sensitive and personal data; Need Analysis Report.

Phase 2. Developing VR System, Curriculum. During this phase will be proposed a model for VR-system, that will be based on a need analysis report. The model will describe the materials, software and platform required to support the youth to figure out their chosen occupation. Leading organisations and partners will revise existing national requirements and regulations concerning necessities for the proposed platforms and software. Also, partners will finalise milestones according to the model. The model will consist of detailed explanations for each step that is going to be completed in the following outputs. All contents for software related work will be designed in this output. In order to complete this output, VR facilities at partner organisations will be used. The partners have a VR lab that includes VR Ready Laptop, Oculus DK2 Kits, Rift and Touch Systems with HTC Vive. In addition, there are OSVR, Samsung Gear, Leap Motion Controller and MS HoloLens that we can use to develop the software. All necessary equipment will be available for us to develop the software.

Moreover, during this phase will be preparing the components of the curricula and tests to supervise its performance.

RAW data: models for VR system, programming code, images, documents related to the development of the VR system (e.g. description of the VR-system functions, based on the Need Analysis Report, legislation and national requirements related to the E-platforms and VR software, quality graphics); feedbacks from target audience; prototype of the VR app; review opinions of target audience related with the development of the VR system.

Processed data: processed data RAW, and other data that does not include any sensitive, personal or private information.

Phase 3. The curriculum will be designed to primarily provide support to youths on how to play the VR system and how to find out his/her suitable occupation from their skills. The proposed structure of the curriculum will give the answer to the question of how to use the VR-System effectively.

The leader of this output and the partners will complete the following tasks:

- Prepare the curriculum design and structure;

- Discuss with the partners if country based factors i.e. cultural differences need to be taken into account;
- Develop a detailed method on how a curriculum will be prepared;
- Prepare an occupation list;
- Prepare the Holland-Riasec-Model related curriculum design and guide.

RAW data: data related to the development of the curricula (design and structure), images, schemes, descriptions of the tasks, description of the VR-system, tools and methodology of education, occupation list, Holland-Riasec-Model and guide.

Processed data: processed data RAW and other data that do not include any sensitive, personal or private information.

Phase 4. Testing and analysis phase. Each partner will run pilot testing procedures in their own country with 25 youths. In this phase, the entire VR system will be tested including the VR platform, curriculum and materials. Feedback will be gathered by each partner country and corresponded to the project leader. The quality level of results will be evaluated. A discussion meeting will be scheduled to review all pilot testing feedback. Within this meeting, pilot testing feedback will be revised and the previous outputs and VR-System will be updated.

The tasks for the pilot testing include:

- Organisation of pilot testing (duration, scope, location, etc.);
- Preparation of the standardised forms and assessment tools;
- Reporting will be completed from the questionnaire and interview analysis as a result of all pilot testing;
- All necessary modifications will be listed and returned to their appropriate activity leader for changes to take place;
- Some of the participants will be contacted to have feedback on the final VR-System and modifications will take place if necessary.

Moreover, partners have 1 conference where previously identified target groups will be invited. During the conference, VR App, Curriculum will be presented to the target groups and will be asked to review and provide their feedback. The target group will be kept posted about the project progress and planned dissemination activities through periodic newsletters and flyers.

As the VR-system platform will be integrated with social media accounts, each user will read and agree with the terms of use, including an explanation about the collection of their data and the use of their data by the VR system. At this point, collaboration with the Data Protection Officer and Ethics Committee may arise to establish the correct management of the sensitive and personal data. Moreover, the creation of the Data Protection Impact Assessment may need to be created.

RAW data: review data, feedback, testing procedures of VR-system after the assignment of the informed consent; documents related to the preparation of the testing phase; answers of the surveys, interviews (video recording with interviewers is not defined yet, it will be described in more detail in the next version of DMP)

Transcription video: in case the video recording, they will be transcripts and processed

Processed data: RAW data after their processing (e.g. anonymization, codification, elimination of all sensitive, personal data that can identify a person); processed transcripts without any sensitive and personal data; lists of the improvements to implement, for evaluation will be collecting data related to the number of youths who download the VR-based game into his/her system.

Phase 5. Dissemination of the results. Project Conference and VR Exhibition. A final conference will be organized at INESC TEC - INSTITUTO DE ENGENHARIA DE SISTEMAS E COMPUTADORES, TECNOLOGIA E CIÊNCIA in Portugal at the end of the project to formally launch the VR-System "Life Skills VR" to youths. Also, VR-Exhibition will be organized in Portugal in

February 2023. Attendees are expected to come from European countries. In this exhibition, users can use and play the developed VR-System and give feedback for the system. Lead partner INESC TEC will bring 100 local youth attendees and each partner will bring 5 foreign attendees. The purpose of this big event is to increase awareness of our VR-System. For that purpose, not just youths but those organizations who are relevant to this field will also be invited so that they can use and disseminate the final outputs of this project. Moreover, the partners are also planning to present Life Skills VR to student organisations such as Campus Party. Campus Party (CP) is an annual week-long, 24-hour-a-day technology festival and LAN Party.

Data: documents related to the dissemination of the results, demonstration of the VR system, organization of the conference, its content, workshops, data related to the number of youths who took part in the pilot study, Number of youths who participate in VR-Exhibition; Number of NGOs, employment agencies, or any other institutions who intends to use the tool in their future work; the number of users who like the game and download it; Number of new projects proposed related to "Life Skills VR".

Other types of data: during the project may be created other types of the data (will be described in future versions of the DMPs)

2. Responsibilities

Supervisors of the project: Centre for Factories of the Future Ltd (C4FF) - United Kingdom

Responsible for the project: Professor Reza Ziarati

Partners:

- Aintek Symvouloi Epicheiriseon Efarmoges Ypsilis Technologias Ekpaidefsi Anonymi Etaireia (IDEC) - Greece
- Fondazione Polo Universitario Grossetano - Italy
- Mediterranean Maritime Research and Training Centre - Malta
- ARTES 4.0 Advanced Robotics and enabling digital Technologies & Systems - Italy
- INESC TEC - the Institute for Systems and Computer Engineering, Technology and Science - Portugal

Research team:

Prof. Reza Ziarati - C4FF

Dr. Lakhvir Singh - C4FF

Ms Sherida Walker - C4FF

Daniele Fantechi - Artes 4

Catia Segnini - Polo

Aris Chronopoulos - Idec

Xenia - Idec

Joseph Meli - Maritime MT

Clementina Cruceli - Artes 4

Prof. Leonel Morgado - INESC TEC

Demetrius Lacet Silva - INESC TEC

Responsible for the collection:

for data analysis, processing and preservation of data: Each partner establishes a responsible person for data collection in his country (more information will be added on the next version of the DMP)

Others Researchers of the Project with access to the data RAW, and to the processed data: all members of the project have access to all data

Responsible for publishing and sharing data: will be defined later

Responsible for DMP creation, update and monitoring: Yulia Karimova (ylaleo@gmail.com); Demetrius Lacet Silva (demetrius.l.silva@inesctec.pt)

All partners and members of the project need to agree with the created DMP and the rules defined therein. The DMP will be created according to the recommendations of the, which in turn, follows RDM and GDPR requirements, such as open-science and FAIR principles.

3. FAIR data

1. Findability

To ensure that the data is findable it will be described according to the Dublin Core standard is a metadata standard aimed at describing digital objects (<http://dublincore.org/>).

All processed data and RAW data that can be opened without any restrictions will be deposited on the repository (will be defined later) (e.g. Zenodo, or RDM INESC TEC). Each published dataset of the project will have Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) assigned by the chosen research data repository to make datasets more findable, accessible and reusable by others. Data will be available during and after the end of the project.

Information related to version control and the name convention of each dataset will be added later on the next version of the DMP.

2. Accessibility

The RAW data will be accessible to all members of the project. RAW data that include sensitive or personal data (questionnaires answers, focus group results) will be processed, anonymized and destroyed as soon as possible. The RAW data will be stored on the specific folder of the file-server drive.inesctec.pt. The RAW data with sensitive and personal data will be stored on the different specific folder of the file-server drive.inesctec.pt with restricted access (people who will have access will be defined later on the next version of the DMP). The questionnaire's answers will be stored as Excel files, spss, or json on the folder together with sensitive and personal data with restricted access for statistical processing (processed and anonymized). More detail will be added later on the next version of the DMP.

The videos of the interviews (if will be created) will be transcribed and after that original videos will be destroyed. They will be accessible only to specific members of the team (which will be defined later) and will be stored in the folder together with sensitive and personal data.

The processed data without any sensitive and personal information will be stored for 5 years after the conclusion of the project on drive.inesctec.pt and will be accessible to all members of the project. Moreover, these data will be open and published without any restrictions on the data repository (that will be defined later) with DOI assignment, but probably only after publishing the

respective papers (will be defined later on the next version of the DMP).

All collected data will be stored and retained only for the necessary period to fulfil the purposes for which they were collected and processed, namely scientific research and publishing.

An internal, internet-based communication platform (<https://lifekillsvr.com/index.php/the-project/>) will be set up by the coordinator to enable storing of project materials and the exchange of views during the project period.

The project website will include all outputs of the project and the list of case studies on how the system has been implemented in partners' organisations and highlight the impact it has on partners' organisations. In addition to this, the required training material on how to use the platform for teachers and students will be created and made available on the project website.

3. Interoperability

To ensure the interoperability of the metadata, we will use the DCMI schema (<https://www.dublincore.org/schemas/>) and/or DataCite Metadata Schema (<https://schema.datacite.org/>) (will be defined later).

Moreover, all datasets will use the same standards for data and format preferred for sharing, such as *.xls/*.xlsx, *.doc/*.docx, *.jpeg, *.pdf, *.spss, *.json to attend interoperability requirements.

4. Reusability

The processed data and RAW data without any sensitive, personal or private information can be reusable without any restrictions and any limit of time. They will be publicly available at the data repository (to be defined later) with license Share-Alike, which allows to (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>):

Share — copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format;

Adapt — remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially.

Under the following terms:

Attribution — You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.

ShareAlike — If you remix, transform, or build upon the material, you must distribute your contributions under the same license as the original.

No additional restrictions — You may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits.

Any sensitive and personal data that RAW data can include will be processed, anonymized and destroyed. This information will never be shared with others.

4. Data security

1. Data recovery processing, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data

The data collected through the research questionnaire from all partner countries (min. 25/partner), Focus groups in partner countries (min. 2/partners) and Interviews with NGO and public bodies in all partner countries will be available only for the members of the project during the period of the project. Sensitive and personal data will be stored in the specific folder (will be defined later), with minimum access to them and will be destroyed as soon as possible after their processing. Videos,

their transcripts and not processed questionnaires answers that contain personal information will be destroyed soon after their processing.

The data collected through research questionnaires will be collected by LimeSurvey and stored on the specific folder on the file-server drive.inesctec.pt, until the end of the data collection period (will be destroyed as soon as possible). All of the information that the participants provide will be treated as confidential and will only be used for research purposes. Their comments will not be identified as belonging to the participants, instead, they will be combined with those gathered from other survey participants, and will be analysed as part of a group. We do not use any of the information they provide for direct marketing or other non-research activities.

Participation is voluntary. The participants are entitled to ask that part, or all, of the record of their involvement in the survey, be deleted or destroyed. Moreover, before participation needs to be assigned informed consent.

All processed data and RAW data without sensitive and personal data will be stored during the 5-10 years on drive.inesctec.pt file-server.

2. Coverage of the ethics review procedure context

All studies are following ethical concerns:

1) All participants will be volunteers who agree to an informed consent form (that exist on the first page of the survey). Data privacy policies and participants' anonymity will be respected, and data reports will ensure full confidentiality.

2) At no time will we ever ask you for any personal details and your responses will always remain confidential and anonymous.

5. Other matters

Participants' anonymity will be guaranteed from the beginning of the study.

The DMP will be monitored at least every 6 months. Monitorization will focus on registering the needed changes in all aspects related to the research data management issues. Moreover, it can also clarify the aspects related to the publication of the datasets on which data repository and their detailed description.

The online project management platform will be used for all updates and checking the progress of partners (<https://lifeskillsvr.com/index.php/the-project/>) and will be one of the tools to disseminate and communicate results of the studies, addressing targets such as common citizens and the community at large. More information will be added later.

This DMP will be published on Zenodo with DOI assignment and will be citable.

The issues related to the IPR ownership of data produced during the project is not established yet (will be defined on the next version of DMP).

During the initial stage of the project, the partnership will review the Erasmus+ Project Results Platform to identify past projects with similar objectives and will invite responsible personnel to discuss possible collaboration opportunities. The partners will also study the good practices and success stories from the past projects relevant to proposed project ideas and will use them as input to "Life Skills VR" Outputs.

The partners will use platforms like eTwinning, Eurodesk, SALTO-YOUTH, Eurydice etc. to promote "Life Skills VR" results among students, researchers, HEIs and other members of target groups.

The project results will be disseminated through online and offline channels. It would include:

- Project Web site. The project Web site will be established early in the project to provide wide dissemination of the project results, publications, and information about the project.
- Social networks such as LinkedIn, Facebook and Twitter and other Electronic information channels (partners' own, and relevant external Web sites and online journals and electronic newsletters) will be used to disseminate the project results to circles of individual contacts and wider potentially interested communities, respectively.
- User Interest Groups. User Interest Groups (UIGs) are already engaged in “Life Skills VR” across 5 European countries.
- EC dissemination activities. The project will make use of the dissemination activities undertaken by the EC and by EC-funded projects in Horizon 2020, and other EC programmes.
- Journals/Conferences/Exhibitions. Journal articles and other publications will be part of the dissemination activities. All partners will publish papers on the project results and will present the project at European and national conferences, conventions and exhibitions.
- Student Fairs. The project consortium will make a list of potential student fairs such as Campus Party, University Employer events etc. at local, regional, national and EU levels.

6. Resources

The partners have a VR lab that includes VR Ready Laptop, Oculus DK2 Kits, Rift and Touch Systems with HTC Vive. In addition, there are OSVR, Samsung Gear, Leap Motion Controller and MS HoloLens that we can use to develop the software. All necessary equipment will be available for us to develop the software.

7. Complementary information

During the project in accordance with the data collection, their processing and analysis the need to create the Data Protection Impact Assessment and collaboration with the Data Protection Officer may emerge. More detailed information about this aspect will be added later in the following versions of the DMP.

The expected data size for preservation will be defined later.

References

1. Esteban M. Aucejo, Jacob French, Maria Paola Ugalde Araya, Basit Zafar, (2020). The impact of COVID-19 on student experiences and expectations: Evidence from a survey, *Journal of Public Economics*, Volume 191, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpubeco.2020.104271>.